

Sorption and Desorption of Crystal Violet on Kaolinite

D. K. De, S. K. Chakravarti* and S. K. Mukherjee

The adsorption and desorption of crystal violet on kaolinite have been studied. The adsorption data fit in with the Langmuir equation up to a concentration of 9.5×10^{-5} M. The distribution and selectivity coefficients increase in the order: $\text{Na}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{++} < \text{Ca}^{++} < \text{Ba}^{++} < \text{H}^+ < < \text{cetyltrimethylammonium ion} < \text{cetylpyridinium ion}$.

The study of dye adsorption on the surface of solids is of considerable interest^{1,2}. Ramchandran *et al.*³ studied the sorption of methylene blue, crystal violet, and malachite green on kaolinite, bentonite and illite surfaces. Hajela and Ghosh measured the adsorption of crystal violet by hydrated ferric oxide⁴ and chromium oxide⁵ in the sol state. Adsorption of methylene blue, methyl violet and other dyes by alumina was studied by Giles *et al.*⁶. But our knowledge of the desorption of these dyes from the mineral-dye complex is meagre. McAttee studied the exchange of dimethyldicetadecylammonium ion and other primary, secondary and tertiary amine salts for dimethylbenzyl laurylammonium ion from its bentonite complex in nonaqueous medium.^{7,8}

In the present communication are reported the results of sorption of crystal violet (CV) on kaolinite and its desorption.

A kaolinite clay fraction (minus 2.0μ) was collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation of Rajmahal kaolinite (available from the Calcutta Minerals Supply Co. Ltd.). After removal of organic matter by treatment with H_2O_2 the clay was converted into the H-form by passing through an H-resin (Amberlite IR-120) column. The base exchange capacity (b.e.c.) determined by titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of normal BaCl_2 is 5.1 m. e. %.

The adsorption of CV by kaolinite was studied by taking 10 ml of a 3.06% suspension in each of several stoppered bottles and then equilibrating with different amounts of the dye solution. For this purpose the mixtures were shaken for 2 hr and kept overnight. Next day they were again shaken for 2 hr. before centrifuging. The dye content in the clear centrifugate was analysed colorimetrically by means of Spekker (Hilger) using buffer pH 4.8. The amount of dye adsorbed was calculated by difference.

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University.

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For the desorption studies the kaolinite-dye complex was prepared by equilibrating kaolinite with a dye solution containing 50% in excess of the b.e.c of the mineral. After adsorption the kaolinite-dye complex was washed with distilled water till optical density of wash liquid was constant. 10ml. of a 2.4% suspension of the kaolinite-CV complex was taken in each of a series of test tubes and different amounts of electrolytes were added. The total volume of the suspension was made up to 12 ml in each case. The overall concentration of the electrolytes was not allowed to exceed 0.05M. The mixtures were shaken and kept overnight. The supernatant liquid was centrifuged and analysed for its dye content as above.

The reagents were of E. Merck quality except CTAB, which was of BDH-AR quality. Calcium and magnesium were titrated with EDTA, and barium was analysed as BaSO₄.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherm of CV on kaolinite is given in Fig. 1, which is characteristic of the Langmuir type. The plot of C/X against C (shown in the same Fig.) is also linear. From the slope of the line the value of the constant V_m (the amount required to form a complete monolayer) is found to be 3.9 m.e./100 gm. The isotherm is drawn up to 3.6 m.e./100 gm, which, being less than the value of V_m , indicates a monomolecular adsorption. The reasonable value of V_m compared to the exchange capacity of kaolinite (5.1 m.e./100 gm) indicates obedience of the adsorption data to the Langmuir equation.

FIG. 1. Adsorption isotherm of CV on Kaolinite.

The results of desorption of CV from its kaolinite complex are given in Figs. 2 and 3. The desorption curves by inorganic ions are alike except that by H⁺ ion. Not only is the amount desorbed by H⁺ ion nearly five times that by other inorganic ions but the nature of the curve is also changed. The anomalous behaviour of H⁺ ion in exchange and other colloid chemical reactions is quite common.

The desorption curves by CP⁺ and CTA⁺ are also unusual. At the initial stage the rate of desorption of CV with respect to concentration of the added electrolyte is small. But afterwards it increases and then gradually flattens out like the usual Langmuir type

of curves. This may be explained in the following way :

FIG. 2. Desorption data of crystal violet from kaolinite-dye complex by different ions, (1) Na^+ , (2) NH_4^+ , (3) K^+ , (4) Mg^{2+} , (5) Ca^{2+} , (6) Ba^{2+} .

FIG. 3. Desorption data of crystal violet from kaolinite-dye complex by (1) CTA^+ , (2) CP^+ , Fig. 3(a) and by H^+ Fig. 3(b).

At low concentrations of the CP^+ and CTA^+ ions, they exchange as single units with the dye ions but after a certain stage, which approximately agree with the critical micelle concentration (c.m.c.) of the electrolytes, they become associated in the adsorbed state making the entry of more ions easier. The sudden change in the slope of the desorption curves probably indicates the concentrations at which micelle formation begins. Of the two ions again CP^+ , having a lower c.m.c. than CTA^+ , desorbs a larger amount of the dye than CTA^+ ^{9,10}. The distribution coefficients were calculated according to the equation $\lambda_i = \frac{\bar{m}_i}{m_i}$ where $\bar{m}_i$ and m_i are the molal concentrations

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of the dye in the solid and solution phases. The selectivity coefficients were calculated at a suitable equilibrium concentration of the desorbing ions according to equation,

$$K_{i_{cv}} = \frac{[CV] [\bar{i}^{z+}]^{1/z}}{[\bar{CV}] [i^{z+}]^{1/z}}$$

corresponding to the equilibrium $\bar{CV} + \frac{1}{z} i^{z+} \rightleftharpoons CV + \frac{1}{z} \bar{i}^{z+}$ where the bars refer to the solid phase, and z is the valency of the desorbing ion. The selectivity coefficient is not a constant quantity but varies with concentration and has been preferably called Selectivity Number. The Selectivity Numbers (Table 1) arrange themselves in the order: $Na^+ < NH_4^+ < K^+ < Mg^{++} < Ca^{++} < Ba^{++} < H^+ < CTA^+ < CP^+$.

TABLE I

Desorption characteristics of CV with respect to different ions on kaolinite

Electrolyte used	Conc. of Electrolyte	Distribution Coefficient	Selectivity Number.
<i>1:1 electrolyte.</i>			
NaCl	$1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$	1.0×10^{-2}	0.84×10^{-6}
NH ₄ Cl	„	2.7×10^{-2}	6.2×10^{-6}
KCl	„	2.9×10^{-2}	7.2×10^{-6}
HCl	„	1.24×10^{-1}	1.35×10^{-4}
<i>1:2 electrolyte.</i>			
MgCl ₂	„	3.8×10^{-2}	6.4×10^{-5}
CaCl ₂	„	3.9×10^{-2}	6.6×10^{-5}
BaCl ₂	„	4.2×10^{-2}	7.3×10^{-5}
<i>Quaternary ammonium salt.</i>			
CTAB	$3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	7.1	1.5×10^{-1}
CPCI	„	9.4	3.6×10^{-1}

Except the position of H⁺ the present series agrees with the order observed in the desorption of methylene blue from the kaolinite-MB complex¹¹.

The measurements were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$. All the glass wares were of pyrex brand, which minimised adsorption of the dye on the walls of the vessels. The interaction of the dye with the surface-active agents¹² was assumed to be small at the concentrations used in these experiments.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF KALYANI,
KALYANI, NADIA,
W. BENGAL.

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